

An FDO-based data exchange web-interface

A visually-enhanced demonstration

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Abstract

Adopting new interfaces, especially those that contain novel representation models, as is the case we are dealing with in [1], can be challenging due to level of expertise required to adopt or integrate such an interface. Often, showcasing the use of a solution is a good approach to bring it to a broader audience, including members with non-technical background. To this end, we developed a web app that demonstrates how to explore the FAIR Digital Object (FDO)-based environment that we have built so far.

This environment consists of several services, all relying on our Application Programming Interface, and includes connections to our partners and RDCs, including supporting services, such as that for FDO registration. As such, our API specification enables the development of different services through this environment. Our demonstration is the first real application that relies on and consumes data from all other services (retrieving data, registering FDOs, etc.).

In contrast to the specification, we aim for a more educational or informative objective, including a visual representation of the data flow for each operation that the user and the data will perform. With it, a user can edit FDOs, and pass them to different services in a drag-and-drop manner. Communication occurs exclusively via FDOs, so every response consists of one or more FDOs. The responses can be modified and passed to another service, enabling the construction of complex workflows. Additionally, the web application includes descriptions as a way to accompany the execution of individual tasks, via predefined instructions, to serve as a self-learning resource that users can complete on their own pace. We decided to include this aspect as part of the process so that one does not have to switch to a different application to present the tasks and provide the necessary context of the FDO-based demonstration but has both the instructions and the workflow in the same service.

The chosen approach provides an additional perspective to the existing environment beyond Web APIs, shell scripts, or interface definitions, which we expect to reach a wider audience, including non-tech-savvy users. Moreover, it demonstrates the (re)use of data (upload once, use multiple times), as users directly and repeatedly interact with the same FDO instance representation. Furthermore, this website is also useful in the

context of service development, as the interaction is visualized. Finally, with the help of the tool, we were able to identify bottlenecks in our test service implementations, increasing the stability of the environment.

The visualization allows both the concept of an FDO-based interaction and the usage of the FAIR-API to be demonstrated effectively. The simple website shows the potential this concept brings to the NFDI environment, also serving as an example for other initiatives. Finally, it can be used beyond the current scope, potentially attracting more interest and engagement in the topic.

Resources

The submission is not based on data. It describes an Application Programming Interface (API) by design.

Author contributions

Roland Johannes: Writing – original draft, services development

Fidan Limani: Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing

Daniel Schiffner: Editing, Conceptualization, Supervision, Project administration

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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References

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